

Wellbeing as a trigger for behavioural change

Insights and policy recommendations from the ACCTING project

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Wellbeing can act as a pivotal driver for behavioural change, leveraging the principles of inclusivity under the Green Deal framework. Evidence from ACCTING's research shows that active transportation, sustainable food systems, and nature-based interventions not only enhance individual health but also foster community resilience and social cohesion. These findings confirm and expand upon existing research (WHO, 2016, 2018, 2020; European Commission, 2019, 2020), showing that changes motivated by wellbeing are more likely to be adopted and sustained, especially if they also address social and cultural factors. However, ACCTING's results emphasise that systemic barriers such as financial constraints, limited infrastructure, and cultural mismatches hinder vulnerable groups from participating in these transformative practices. Findings from ACCTING pilot projects demonstrate how inclusive strategies, like community gardens and cycling programmes, can address these barriers while inspiring change through relatable stories and public campaigns. Moreover, pilot projects bring new evidence of how wellbeing considerations not only increase participation but also support social cohesion, addressing a knowledge gap on the intersection of social equity, health, and environmental sustainability. At the same time, it requires integrating wellbeing into policies, promoting accessible transportation, supporting community-driven initiatives, and using storytelling to inspire collective action.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are based on the results from ACCTING’s research and co-creation workshops. They are primarily targeted towards policymakers (local, regional, national, and EU level). However, several recommendations are also relevant for civil society organisations, community groups, transport and mobility providers, and academic institutions:

Integrate wellbeing metrics into policy frameworks

Policies can benefit from incorporating wellbeing metrics to better address the interconnected challenges of health, environmental sustainability, and social equity. Research demonstrates that integrating wellbeing into policy frameworks, such as urban mobility plans and environmental programmes, can create co-benefits for public health and environmental sustainability (Chapman and Howden–Chapman, 2021). For example, urban mobility plans can include metrics such as **reductions in cardio-vascular and stress-related illnesses and increased physical activity levels**. While environmental programmes can measure improvements in community cohesion and emotional resilience, alongside emission reductions. This approach not only aligns with decarbonisation goals but also ensures that wellbeing improvements are integral to measuring the success of sustainability initiatives.

Promote active and accessible transportation with a focus on wellbeing

Comprehensive networks of pedestrian pathways, cycling lanes and affordable public transit systems play a significant role in supporting both physical and mental wellbeing. These infrastructures can be complemented by initiatives such as bike-sharing programmes, community walking groups, and active commuting campaigns that highlight benefits like stress reduction, improved fitness, and stronger social connections. Ensuring accessibility is also essential, with transport options tailored to meet the needs of vulnerable populations such as older adults, low-income groups, and caregivers. Such

measures can promote independence, reduce mobility-related anxiety, and encourage equitable participation in sustainable practices. Communication tools such as mobility apps and other

technological solutions, can complement these measures by providing personalised information on health benefits, e.g., calories burned or exposure to pollutants. This can further motivate individuals to adopt sustainable transportation choices (Marquart and Schuppan, 2021).

Foster cross-sectoral collaboration for sustainable wellbeing

Integrated planning across sectors such as mobility, health, social welfare and environmental protection, can help create more cohesive and effective solutions. For example, linking active transportation policies with health promotion campaigns could encourage physical activity while reducing reliance on motorised vehicles. Multi-stakeholder platforms involving policymakers, businesses and NGOs can provide opportunities to co-design initiatives that address both environmental sustainability and wellbeing, ensuring a collaborative approach to meeting diverse community needs.

Support community-driven sustainability initiatives that promote wellbeing-focused campaigns

Financial support, resources, and capacity-building workshops should be provided for grassroots projects like urban gardening, tree planting, and food-sharing programmes. As highlighted by Baker and colleagues (2024), these are effective ways to reduce eco-anxiety and foster social bonds. Moreover, they can help foster partnerships between local governments and community organisations to tackle multidimensional challenges such as food security, green space access, and social isolation.

Policies/actions should focus on improving the affordability and accessibility of sustainable food options

To make sustainable food options accessible, especially for low-income groups, one option is subsidising plant-based and locally sourced foods and using wellbeing as a motivator for this policy change. To support this further, collaborating with community-driven initiatives like urban gardens and food literacy workshops can enhance social connections and raise awareness of the nutritional and emotional benefits of sustainable diets. Additionally, campaigns can emphasise the mental and physical advantages of nutritious and ecological food, including higher energy levels, reduced chronic disease risk, and increased life satisfaction. To successfully address diverse income groups, the messages can integrate multiple values, like social justice, environmental sustainability and animal welfare, to make sustainable diets appealing and accessible to all.

Findings from ACCTING

Existing research has long demonstrated that economic constraints significantly affect people's ability to adopt healthier and more sustainable diets. Studies such as Capstick et al. (2022) highlight those individuals with limited income often focus on affordability over health or sustainability, contributing to lower rates of pro-environmental behaviours. Civil society organisations (CSOs) have built on these findings to encourage supermarkets to offer lower-cost organic products – an example of how evidence-based advocacy can shape market trends (Parekh and Klintman, 2021).

Findings from ACCTING's research line 6 (Values associated with Environmentally Sustainable Food Consumption) confirms this pattern showing that **changing food values could lead to behavioural change in food consumption**. Specifically, food values relating to animal welfare (e.g., pain-free production), environmental welfare (e.g., is produced without disturbing the balance of nature), and health (e.g., is good for my skin, teeth, hair, nails, etc.) showed the strongest correlations with sustainable (seasonal and plant-based food) food consumption. However, our findings also show that **economic barriers heavily influence food-related behavioural change and access to sustainable options**. Income disparities influence food values and consumption patterns, with low-income groups prioritising affordability over health, wellbeing and sustainability; thus, consuming fewer plant-based foods.

The second key finding from this research line is that **participation in bottom-up initiatives (BUIs)** is associated with **change towards giving greater importance to health and environmental (animal welfare) food values, as well as to consuming more environmentally sustainable food (seasonal and plant-based)**. People who reported greater participation in different kinds of food- and environment-related activism and social movements more often report that they value food that is produced in environmentally sustainable, socially just, and animal-friendly ways.

ACCTING's research lines 7 and 8 on transport poverty and sustainable travel similarly highlight the critical role of wellbeing in promoting behavioural change towards sustainable mobility, particularly among vulnerable populations. **Transitioning from motorised vehicles to active mobility options contributes to reduced stress, improved physical activity, and enhanced social connectivity**. However, structural barriers, such as inadequate infrastructure, high transportation costs, and safety concerns disproportionately impact economically and socially marginalised groups, limiting their ability to participate in these practices. These challenges are particularly evident in regions with insufficient public transport systems or cycling networks.

Better Stories

In ACCTING we use 'better stories', a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis¹, to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Walk the City² is a women-led ecological association in Prague concerned with the development of walking as a means of transport, air pollution, and the regulation of car traffic. Particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic, they have emphasised the importance of developing a walkable city. Initially, they were focused on women and the barriers they face in urban mobility, but in time this expanded to also include other groups. They advocate for the protection of pedestrians, in particular older people and children on their way to school, the promotion of walking as a healthy and sustainable means of transport, and the improvement of public spaces. An example of one of their actions consists of collaborating with schools to organise events where children and their parents are 'challenged' to walk to school as often as possible emphasising that "it is a great opportunity to move". They support these kinds of events by trying to make streets and public spaces safer for children. In this way, behavioural change towards more sustainable mobility is promoted.

Sindikata Biciklista (Cyclists Union)³ is an NGO that organises various activities around mobility and cycling. Their goal is to improve bicycle-based mobility (and other sustainable forms) to facilitate the uptake of sustainable and healthy transport options. They promote healthy and sustainable forms of mobility, including cycling and walking, through activities like policy advocacy, promoting cycling culture, and carrying out educational campaigns. In their educational activities, they emphasise health benefits and teach ways to reduce tensions between cyclists and pedestrians (who are often competing for the same limited space) as well as how to combine cycling with public transport.

MindFood⁴ is an organisation that offers the opportunity to engage in food-growing activities (among other pursuits) to people struggling with mental health issues, with the goal of making edible gardening more inclusive and accessible, while being supportive of people's overall (mental) wellbeing. Based in West London, the initiative engages in ecotherapy with people who either signed up themselves or were referred by a GP. The main activity that is offered consists of a six-week course consisting of weekly sessions that aim to reduce depression, stress and anxiety through edible gardening. After involvement in the programme, most participants are found to have implemented positive

¹ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

² <https://peskymestem.cz/en/>

³ <https://sindikatabiciklista.hr/o-nama/>

⁴ <https://www.mindfood.org.uk/>

changes in their diets, and to display increases in (self-reported) wellbeing and physical health measurements.

Toques en stock⁵ is a French association that aims to organise regular cooking workshops to counter food insecurity among vulnerable segments of the population. These cooking workshops offer people access to healthy food and teach them how to cook their own, while minimising food waste by recycling afterwards. Target groups of the initiative include people (mostly women) who live in temporary emergency accommodation in the broader Paris region (i.e., refugees, people with very low or no income, survivors of trafficking or exploitation, etc.). This means that the recipes that are used are adapted to their limited circumstances in terms of available equipment.

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About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

Running until May 2025 and based on two research cycles, ACCTING mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies.

Find out more about the project and discover more factsheets at <https://accting.eu>

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Authorship and contributions

Authors: Dilay Çelebi Gonidis (SEERC), Aart Kerremans (YW), Nikita Sharma (ECSA)

Contributors: YW, ECSA, and contributions from the ACCTING consortium.

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